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1 M5.1 - Reference collection of test data sets

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Dissemination Level

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2 Versioning and contribution history

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0.1	07.02.2023	Maaïke Verburg (DANS)	Set-up and TOC
0.2	02.03.2023	Robert Huber (UBremen)	Report draft
1.0	03.03.2023	Robert Huber (UBremen), Maaïke Verburg (DANS)	Finalising and submitting

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TERMINOLOGY

Terminology/Acronym	Description
EOSC	European Open Science Cloud
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable
GA	Grant Agreement to the project
SSH	Social Sciences and Humanities

4 Introduction

One of the main objectives of FAIR-IMPACT is the realisation of a FAIR EOSC, i.e. the implementation of an integrated FAIR ecosystem providing FAIR data and services. A particular focus is on supporting the implementation of FAIR-enabled practices in diverse scientific communities to create the conditions for a diversity of FAIR research outputs.

Task 5.1 *FAIR digital object assessment pilots in a disciplinary context* aims to enable the verification of the FAIRness of digital objects in a discipline-specific context. This requires discipline-specific metrics and tests to assess discipline-specific FAIRness. In Deliverable 5.1 *Implementing metrics for automated FAIR digital objects assessment in a disciplinary context*, discipline-specific metrics for the social sciences have been provided to this end. This project output is currently submitted for internal review and will be publicly available soon. To verify the correct implementation of these newly developed discipline-specific FAIR metrics and tests in FAIR assessment tools like F-UJI¹, a selection of test objects (i.e. data sets) is necessary against which the results of the tool can be verified.

This is the purpose of the *Reference collection of test data sets* compiled within the FAIR-IMPACT use cases and which is reported on in this milestone report.

¹ F-UJI: Automated FAIR Data Assessment Tool. Access to the tool's Github Repository: <https://github.com/pangaea-data-publisher/fuji> Web-based client: <https://www.f-ujii.net/>

5 Description of the Milestone

The Milestone essentially consists of a collection of links to social science data sets. These are intended to verify the implementation of the discipline-specific metrics for the social sciences presented in D.5.1 (internal review, to be finalised and published in M10). The selection of data sets was chosen, reviewed, and provided by representatives of the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) integrated use case partner, namely CESSDA (represented by UESSEX-UKDS explicitly, but also task partner KNAW-DANS) and supplemented by other relevant social sciences datasets by project partners (e.g., UEDIN-DCC).

The reference collection is intended as a living document, to be further extended and reviewed to create an accurate representation of the community the metrics intend to tailor to (social sciences). The reference collection is intended to reflect multiple different data types, volumes, and other characteristics that are often encountered in this community.

The reference collection approach will also be applied to other communities that this task will explore over the course of the project. For each new community that metrics are drafted for, a collection of reference data sets will be compiled as a means of verification.

5.1 Role of the milestone

The collection of test data sets presented will be used to test the discipline-specific metrics developed in Task 5.1 and the FAIR assessment tests implemented for these in F-UJI. These metrics were initially developed for the SSH use case and aim to test data sets from the social sciences. This collection is intended to provide an initial overview of the domain-agnostic FAIRness of the data sets it contains. On the other hand, the implementation of the discipline-specific tests in F-UJI is to be checked on the basis of the data sets. They also provide a means of benchmarking assessment tools for discipline-specific tests. Furthermore, the collection can be used to inform data providers about possibilities to make discipline-specific FAIR requirements more machine-readable.

5.1.1 Means of verification

The means of verification for this Milestone as per the GA is to have the reference collection available. The collection is currently available internally for the project partners only. After the initial testing with F-UJI and further curation of the collection, the document will also become available to the larger public.

6 Conclusions and next steps

The collection of test data sets represents an important milestone for the verification of the metrics from D5.1. The deliverable is currently in project internal review and will be available for public comment thereafter. After completion of this consultation phase, we intend to adapt F-UJI accordingly to implement discipline-specific tests. We will use the test data sets to improve F-UJI in an iterative process, but also to optimise the test data sets so that they correspond to the ideas of FAIRness of the social sciences.